

A WIDE PERSPECTIVE ON DIABETIC FOOT TREATMENT - A REVIEW PAPER.

1. Piotr Kalisz¹ [PK], ORCID <https://orcid.org/0009-0000-1564-4229>

¹ Independent Public Healthcare Centre in Myślenice, ul. Szpitalna 2, 32-400 Myślenice

2. Bartłomiej Gałuszka² [BG], ORCID <https://orcid.org/0009-0006-1426-6709>

² Independent Public Health Care Facility, Municipal Hospitals Complex in Chorzów: Chorzów, PL

3. Magdalena Kałucka-Janik³ [MK], ORCID <https://orcid.org/0009-0006-5389-0993>

³ Independent Public Health Care Facility, Municipal Hospitals Complex in Chorzów: Chorzów, PL

4. Aleksandra Kapral⁴ [AK], ORCID <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-6302-1127>

⁴ Independent Public Health Care Facility, Municipal Hospitals Complex in Chorzów: Chorzów, PL

5. Krzysztof Kościański⁵ [KK], ORCID <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-7566-5810>

⁵ University Clinical Hospital No.2 of Pomeranian Medical University in Szczecin, Szczecin, PL

6. Patryk Król⁶ [PK], ORCID <https://orcid.org/0009-0003-3753-3978>

⁶ University Clinical Hospital No.2 of Pomeranian Medical University in Szczecin, Szczecin, PL

7. Michał Pogoda⁷ [MP], ORCID <https://orcid.org/0009-0000-2936-4367>

⁷ Pomeranian Medical University in Szczecin, Rybacka 1, 70-204, Szczecin, PL

8. Wiktor Daniszewski⁸ [WD], ORCID <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-1767-7768>

⁸ Independent Public Voivodeship Integrated Hospital in Szczecin, ul.Arkońska 4, Szczecin, PL

9. Wiktoria Knobelsdorf⁹ [WK], ORCID <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-2652-7447>

⁹ University Clinical Hospital No. 1 of Pomeranian Medical University in Szczecin, Szczecin, Poland

10. Katarzyna Zając¹⁰, ORCID <https://orcid.org/0009-0000-2056-8128>

¹⁰ Specialist Hospital No. 2 in Bytom, Bytom, Poland

Abstract

Background

Diabetic foot syndrome is a late complication of diabetes. It is estimated to occur in one in four patients with diabetes. Treatment is difficult, and complications affect mortality, disability, quality of life and the burden on the healthcare system. Comprehensive treatment of the foot at various stages of the disease is needed, including pharmacological and non-pharmacological methods. The review will present various treatment methods and their advantages and limitations.

Aim

The review aims to show the diversity of treatments for diabetic foot syndrome and the benefits of choosing particular methods.

Material and Methods

This systematic review analyses scientific publications on the treatment of diabetic foot syndrome. Data were collected from articles in the PubMed database published between 2020 and 2025. Cohort studies, systematic reviews and meta-analyses were included, with an emphasis on the quality and transparency of the methodology.

Results

The treatment of diabetic foot syndrome has undergone many changes over the years. The range of methods used has expanded significantly, thanks to the multidirectional action of drugs, for example. In addition, new methods have been developed and are practised in specialist centres. The treatment of this condition is coordinated by many specialists, and the development of individual methods allows for personalisation of treatment. This work allows for the condensation and summarisation of information on the treatment of diabetic foot syndrome.

Conclusion

The treatment of diabetic foot is constantly evolving, and the number and profile of different methods is so wide that it allows for the treatment of patients with different forms of the condition and takes into account additional individual risk factors or complications.

Keywords

diabetes, diabetes complications, diabetic foot, diabetology, diabetes treatment

1. Introduction

Diabetic foot syndrome is a late complication of diabetes associated with neuropathy and peripheral arterial disease. This term covers all pathological changes in the foot of a person with diabetes, such as calluses, ulcers and necrosis [1]. It is estimated that diabetic foot syndrome occurs in every fourth patient diagnosed with diabetes [2]. A significant problem in the course of this condition is the formation of ulcers, which are susceptible to infection. Approximately 50-60% of ulcers develop an infection, which is the main factor contributing to the destruction of the diabetic foot. In turn, infections often lead to amputation of the limb at various levels. The treatment of patients with diabetic foot syndrome is a huge challenge. Pathological changes in the diabetic foot contribute to high mortality, increased global disability, decreased quality of life, and increased economic burden on the healthcare system [3]. Accordingly, there is a need for comprehensive treatment of the foot at every stage of the disease process. The therapy uses pharmacological methods, but also numerous non-pharmacological methods. The following overview aims to show the diversity and multitude of solutions in the effective treatment of diabetic foot syndrome, as well as to summarise the advantages and limitations of each method.

2. Research material and methods

This systematic review is based on an analysis of available scientific publications on methods of treating diabetic foot syndrome, a common complication of diabetes. The aim of the study was to present various pharmacological and non-pharmacological methods, their characteristics, as well as their advantages and disadvantages. The data came from articles in databases such as PubMed published between 2020 and 2025. Cohort studies, systematic reviews and meta-analyses were included, with attention paid to the quality and transparency of the methodology of the data presented.

3. Results

3.1 Pharmacological methods

3.1.1 Glycaemic control, lipid levels, blood pressure, weight normalisation, drugs improving blood circulation

Blood glucose control in the context of diabetic foot is the cornerstone of pharmacological treatment. In recent years, new drugs have appeared on the market that have significantly expanded treatment options. In addition to the long-used metformin, oral treatment includes SGLT2 inhibitors, DPP-4 inhibitors and GLP-1 analogues. SGLT2 inhibitors and GLP-1 analogues provide additional support in the treatment of diabetic kidney disease. The HbA1c parameter is an indicator of diabetes control. Patients taking insulin require special attention from diabetologists in order to establish optimal insulin therapy correlated with diet, lifestyle and other factors [4]. Metabolic control in the context of lipids significantly reduces cardiovascular risk in patients with diabetes and is an important component of long-term treatment of diabetic foot. Statins are the most effective treatment, followed by PCSK9 inhibitors and statins in combination with ezetimibe. LDL-C is a reliable indicator of hypercholesterolemia treatment [5]. The coexistence of diabetes and hypertension is a common phenomenon. Uncontrolled, high blood pressure is a significant risk factor for cardiovascular disease. Most studies indicate that reducing systolic blood pressure below 140 mmHg is beneficial in reducing the risk of circulatory complications [6]. Treatment of hypertension must be personalised, but ACE inhibitors or sartans should be the dominant drugs in patients with diabetes [7]. Normalisation of body weight is a fundamental principle in the treatment of diabetes and its complications. In addition to non-pharmacological methods, it is worth mentioning GLP-1 analogues and tirzepatide, which are currently the most effective in reducing body weight [8]. A large number of patients with diabetes suffer from peripheral artery disease, which can lead to diabetic foot and ulcers. There are reports of the beneficial effects of aspirin and cilostazol in people with diabetic foot syndrome. These drugs are effective in alleviating the symptoms of peripheral artery disease and also have a significant impact on the treatment of diabetic foot [9].

3.1.2 Treatment of infections

When an ulcer appears in a diabetic foot, the infection can develop rapidly due to circulatory disorders and impaired immune response. It is also possible for the infection to spread to the connective tissue and subsequently to osteomyelitis or necrotising fasciitis. Gram-positive bacteria are most commonly isolated from wounds: group B streptococci and Enterococcus [10]. The basis of treatment is systemic antibiotic therapy. In most cases, the use of topical antibiotics does not bring additional benefits [11]. The choice of antibiotic is based on culture results. Some sources indicate that empirical antibiotic therapy can be used in mild diabetic

foot infections, but the aim is to practise targeted antibiotic therapy based on culture [12]. In mild infections, oral antibiotic therapy can be used. In more severe cases, broad-spectrum intravenous antibiotics are used [13].

3.2 Non-pharmacological methods

3.2.1 Limb offloading and orthopaedic treatment

Sensory disturbances resulting from neuropathy and high mechanical stress on foot tissues are the most common causes of ZSC. Therefore, it is necessary to use devices that relieve pressure on the foot [14]. One such device is a non-removable full-contact plaster cast (TCC), which is the gold standard in pressure relief treatment. However, the use of this method carries the risk of infection, ischaemia and patient reluctance. Alternatively, removable orthoses such as VACOPed are used. It is a biomechanically stable device, comparable to TCC [15]. It is worth noting that the correct selection of cushioning hardness significantly reduces pressure. It is important to personalise the device in relation to the location of the wound, the patient's weight and individual needs [16].

3.2.2 Surgical procedures

All surgical procedures on the diabetic foot constitute a group of invasive treatment methods. Most often, surgical treatment consists of mechanical wound cleansing, applying special dressings and using antimicrobial agents. Wounds are divided into three categories: healing, non-healing and requiring supportive treatment. Non-healing wounds are those that cannot be healed within 8 weeks – in such cases, advanced, non-invasive treatment methods are used, which are described later in this paper [17]. Surgical interventions involve wound cleaning, but also decompression and drainage of purulent secretions. In the case of bone and joint infections, bone resection is used and amputation is avoided if possible [18]. Surgical reconstruction also appears to be an interesting method. Reconstructions are used in cases of failed ulcer healing despite the use of offloading therapy. The two main methods are flexor tendon tenotomy for ulcers on the tips of the smaller toes and Achilles tendon lengthening, which reduces the risk of recurrence of plantar ulcers in the forefoot [19].

3.2.3 Vascular surgery

In diabetic foot syndrome, arterial circulation disorders in the lower limbs should always be taken into account. It is very important to note that early revascularisation can prevent up to 80% of lower limb amputations. The method of revascularisation using vascular and endovascular surgery depends on the location and length of the occlusion. Vascular bypassing, vascular recanalisation using stents or hybrid treatment are used [20]. It should be remembered that time is of the essence in arterial revascularisation. Only half of patients with chronic life-threatening ischaemia undergo revascularisation, and only 25 per cent of them undergo diagnostic imaging in the form of angiography. Often, patients are too ill, arrive too late, or revascularisation is not technically possible. [21].

3.2.4 Hyperbaric chamber

Hyperbaric oxygen therapy can be a tool for the active treatment of diabetic foot syndrome. The mechanism of therapy is based on promoting wound healing by increasing the concentration of oxygen dissolved in plasma and delivering oxygen to tissues. The effect of the treatment also includes stimulation of new blood vessel formation and an antibacterial effect on anaerobic bacteria [22]. The method is used in cases of resistant wounds, in combination with standard wound care methods [23]. The use of a hyperbaric chamber improves the prognosis for diabetic foot and, as a result, prevents lower limb amputations [24].

3.2.5 Negative pressure therapy

Negative pressure wound therapy (NPWT) is a method that can be used to treat superficial wounds and drain deep wounds. NPWT is a mechanical unit connected to a tube and a suction device that creates negative pressure between the wound and the surrounding area. The use of this therapy can lead to the removal of necrotic tissue and secretions from wounds, stimulate granulation tissue production, reduce wound infection and improve healing. The negative pressure method improves the wound microenvironment, promotes endothelial cell regeneration and has an advantage over traditional dressings, which easily stick to the wound, damaging granulation tissue and delaying wound healing. For this dressing to work properly, the appropriate negative pressure must be maintained and the wound must be tightly closed. Failure to comply with these rules increases the tendency for the wound to bleed [25].

3.2.6 Growth factors

Fibroblast growth factors (FGFs) are a family of signalling proteins that mediate various processes through their specific receptors. These processes, such as angiogenesis, wound healing and metabolic regulation, are used in the treatment of diabetic foot. In recent years, new research on FGF has led to the increasingly frequent use of topical FGF. In patients with diabetic foot syndrome, the levels of various growth factors change, so the healing process can be accelerated by regulating the level of the growth factor. The use of preparations with growth factors brings good therapeutic effects. The limitations of FGF use are its short half-life and the need for repeated administration. Chronic wounds are characterised by a strong proteolytic environment, which means that growth factors can be degraded. However, there are reports of new, improved FGF carriers, such as special dressings, which will have a beneficial effect on the use of this therapy [26].

3.2.7 Use of skin substitutes

Contrary to appearances, skin substitutes and biological dressings are readily available and safe. They are used in the treatment of large, difficult-to-heal wounds. Skin substitutes can be divided into many groups based on their composition, source of origin and possible additives. Biomaterials can be biological, synthetic or a mixture of both. The materials may come from the transplant recipient, another human donor or be derived from another animal species. Skin substitutes supported by stem cells or their fragments may be a beneficial treatment option for diabetic foot syndrome [27].

3.2.8 Larvae therapy

Larval wound cleansing therapy is an unusual method of treating diabetic foot wounds. Its popularity is growing due to increasing resistance to antibiotics, which forces the use of other treatment methods. This method involves applying approximately 10 sterilised larvae per square centimetre of wound and covering it with a sterile dressing [28]. This therapy achieves satisfactory treatment results. In the cited study (Siavash et al), complete wound healing occurred in 83% of patients undergoing therapy [29]. In cases that are particularly resistant to conventional treatment methods, this therapy remains an effective alternative.

4. Discussion

The above work summarises many modern and key methods of treating diabetic foot syndrome. The topic presented seems to be an important issue due to its prevalence in the population. Diabetic foot syndrome is a highly diverse disease entity, and the choice of therapy depends on many factors. The choice of treatment method requires the cooperation of specialists from many fields. The treatment team should include specialists in general surgery, vascular surgery, angiology, diabetology, microbiology, clinical pharmacology, nursing, podiatry, physiotherapy, dietetics and psychology. Treatment should be multidirectional, and simple methods such as relieving pressure on the lower limb are often just as important as pharmacotherapy and advanced surgical methods. In therapy, the speed of implementation of individual elements of treatment is important, which is why physical examination and patient assessment, coordinated by a diabetologist, are essential. It is extremely important to regularly and thoroughly examine the feet of patients with diabetes during routine check-ups. Another important factor is patient education, as patients should be encouraged to care for and maintain foot hygiene. Educating patients and teaching them how to care for their feet is not expensive and can largely prevent problems associated with diabetic foot [30]. There are specific questionnaires that can be helpful in determining the risk of severe forms of diabetic foot syndrome. These questionnaires include risk factors for diabetic foot. Risk factors such as advanced age, poor glycaemic control, long duration of diabetes, and existing vascular disease require us to be particularly vigilant for the onset of diabetic foot symptoms [31]. Many methods of treating diabetic foot syndrome offer patients the opportunity to choose a personalized treatment method depending on their comorbidities, preferences and lifestyle.

5. Conclusions

The modern treatment methods described in this paper show how much has been discovered so far in the field of diabetic foot treatment, even though many therapies, such as growth factor therapy, remain the subject of intensive research. It is very important that one therapy does not exclude another, and the multitude of solutions gives patients a chance of successful treatment. Avoiding risk factors and early detection of changes in the foot remain the basic methods of prevention, while modern methods of treating diabetic foot significantly reduce the risk of serious complications in patients diagnosed with diabetes.

Disclosure

Authors' contributions

All authors have read and agreed with the published version of the manuscript.

Funding Statement

The study did not receive any specific funding.

Conflict of Interest Statement

No conflicts of interest.

Informed Consent Statement

Not applicable.

Ethics Committee Statement

Not applicable.

References:

1. Morbach S, Eckhard M, Lobmann R, Müller E, Reike H, Risse A, Rügenapf G, Spraul M. Diabetic Foot Syndrome. *Exp Clin Endocrinol Diabetes*. 2023 Feb;131(1-02):84-93. doi: 10.1055/a-1946-3838. Epub 2023 Jan 31. PMID: 36720238.
2. Anwander H, Vonwyl D, Hecht V, Tannast M, Kurze C, Krause F. Risk Factors for Failure After Surgery in Patients With Diabetic Foot Syndrome. *Foot Ankle Orthop*. 2023 Jul 8;8(3):24730114231182656. doi: 10.1177/24730114231182656. PMID: 37435393; PMCID: PMC10331347.
3. Edmonds M, Manu C, Vas P. The current burden of diabetic foot disease. *J Clin Orthop Trauma*. 2021 Feb 8;17:88-93. doi: 10.1016/j.jcot.2021.01.017. PMID: 33680841; PMCID: PMC7919962.
4. Taylor SI, Yazdi ZS, Beitelshes AL. Pharmacological treatment of hyperglycemia in type 2 diabetes. *J Clin Invest*. 2021 Jan 19;131(2):e142243. doi: 10.1172/JCI142243. PMID: 33463546; PMCID: PMC7810496.
5. Ma CX, Ma XN, Guan CH, Li YD, Mauricio D, Fu SB. Cardiovascular disease in type 2 diabetes mellitus: progress toward personalized management. *Cardiovasc Diabetol*. 2022 May 14;21(1):74. doi: 10.1186/s12933-022-01516-6. PMID: 35568946; PMCID: PMC9107726.
6. Kim HJ, Kim KI. Blood Pressure Target in Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus. *Diabetes Metab J*. 2022 Sep;46(5):667-674. doi: 10.4093/dmj.2022.0215. Epub 2022 Sep 19. PMID: 36193727; PMCID: PMC9532171.
7. Kumar V, Agarwal S, Saboo B, Makkar B. RISSDI Guidelines for the management of hypertension in patients with diabetes mellitus. *Int J Diabetes Dev Ctries*. 2022 Oct;42(4):576-605. doi: 10.1007/s13410-022-01143-7. Epub 2022 Dec 15. PMID: 36536953; PMCID: PMC9750845.
8. Yao H, Zhang A, Li D, Wu Y, Wang CZ, Wan JY, Yuan CS. Comparative effectiveness of GLP-1 receptor agonists on glycaemic control, body weight, and lipid profile for type 2 diabetes: systematic review and network meta-analysis. *BMJ*. 2024 Jan 29;384:e076410. doi: 10.1136/bmj-2023-076410. PMID: 38286487; PMCID: PMC10823535.

9. Jayalal JA, Kumar S, Mohan A. Effects of Cilostazol and Aspirin on Diabetic Foot Ulcer and Peripheral Artery Disease: A Retrospective Study. *Cureus*. 2025 Mar 20;17(3):e80929. doi: 10.7759/cureus.80929. PMID: 40255702; PMCID: PMC12009474.
10. Matheson EM, Bragg SW, Blackwelder RS. Diabetes-Related Foot Infections: Diagnosis and Treatment. *Am Fam Physician*. 2021 Oct 1;104(4):386-394. PMID: 34652105.
11. Soldevila-Boixader L, Fernández AP, Laguna JM, Uçkay I. Local Antibiotics in the Treatment of Diabetic Foot Infections: A Narrative Review. *Antibiotics (Basel)*. 2023 Jan 9;12(1):124. doi: 10.3390/antibiotics12010124. PMID: 36671326; PMCID: PMC9854429.
12. Schmidt BM, Kaye KS, Armstrong DG, Pop-Busui R. Empirical Antibiotic Therapy in Diabetic Foot Ulcer Infection Increases Hospitalization. *Open Forum Infect Dis*. 2023 Oct 5;10(10):ofad495. doi: 10.1093/ofid/ofad495. PMID: 37849506; PMCID: PMC10578503.
13. Raja JM, Maturana MA, Kayali S, Khouzam A, Efeovbokhan N. Diabetic foot ulcer: A comprehensive review of pathophysiology and management modalities. *World J Clin Cases*. 2023 Mar 16;11(8):1684-1693. doi: 10.12998/wjcc.v11.i8.1684. PMID: 36970004; PMCID: PMC10037283.
14. Bus SA, Armstrong DG, Crews RT, Gooday C, Jarl G, Kirketerp-Moller K, Viswanathan V, Lazzarini PA. Guidelines on offloading foot ulcers in persons with diabetes (IWGDF 2023 update). *Diabetes Metab Res Rev*. 2024 Mar;40(3):e3647. doi: 10.1002/dmrr.3647. Epub 2023 May 25. PMID: 37226568.
15. Lim WT, Robinson H, Jude E, Rajbhandari S. The Real-Life Outcome of VACOPed Boot in the Management of Diabetic Foot Ulcers. *Int J Low Extrem Wounds*. 2022 Sep;21(3):290-293. doi: 10.1177/1534734620942671. Epub 2020 Jul 31. PMID: 32734794.
16. Chatzistergos PE, Gatt A, Formosa C, Farrugia K, Chockalingam N. Optimised cushioning in diabetic footwear can significantly enhance their capacity to reduce plantar pressure. *Gait Posture*. 2020 Jun;79:244-250. doi: 10.1016/j.gaitpost.2020.05.009. Epub 2020 May 17. PMID: 32454304.
17. Parveen K, Hussain MA, Anwar S, Elagib HM, Kausar MA. Comprehensive review on diabetic foot ulcers and neuropathy: Treatment, prevention and management. *World J Diabetes*. 2025 Mar 15;16(3):100329. doi: 10.4239/wjd.v16.i3.100329. PMID: 40093290; PMCID: PMC11885961.
18. Senneville É, Albalawi Z, van Asten SA, Abbas ZG, Allison G, Aragón-Sánchez J, Embil JM, Lavery LA, Alhasan M, Oz O, Uçkay I, Urbančič-Rovan V, Xu ZR, Peters EJG. IWGDF/IDSA guidelines on the diagnosis and treatment of diabetes-related foot infections (IWGDF/IDSA 2023). *Diabetes Metab Res Rev*. 2024 Mar;40(3):e3687. doi: 10.1002/dmrr.3687. Epub 2023 Oct 1. PMID: 37779323.
19. Armstrong DG, Tan TW, Boulton AJM, Bus SA. Diabetic Foot Ulcers: A Review. *JAMA*. 2023 Jul 3;330(1):62-75. doi: 10.1001/jama.2023.10578. PMID: 37395769; PMCID: PMC10723802.
20. Rümenapf G, Morbach S, Rother U, Uhl C, Görtz H, Böckler D, Behrendt CA, Hochlenert D, Engels G, Hohneck A, Sigl M; Kommission PAVK und Diabetisches Fußsyndrom der DGG e. V.. Diabetisches Fußsyndrom – Teil 2 : Revaskularisation, Behandlungsalternativen, Versorgungsstrukturen, Rezidivprophylaxe [Diabetic foot syndrome-Part 2 : Revascularization, treatment alternatives, care structures, recurrency prophylaxis]. *Chirurg*. 2021 Feb;92(2):173-186. German. doi: 10.1007/s00104-020-01313-5. PMID: 33237367; PMCID: PMC7875854.
21. Ruemenapf G, Morbach S, Sigl M. Therapeutic Alternatives in Diabetic Foot Patients without an Option for Revascularization: A Narrative Review. *J Clin Med*. 2022 Apr 12;11(8):2155. doi: 10.3390/jcm11082155. PMID: 35456247; PMCID: PMC9032488.
22. Apolo-Arenas MD, Guerrero-Nogales L, Díaz-Muñoz CL, Caro-Puértolas B, Parraca JA, Caña-Pino A. Use of the Hyperbaric Chamber Versus Conventional Treatment for the Prevention of Amputation in Chronic Diabetic Foot and the Influence on Fitting and Rehabilitation: A Systematic Review. *Int J Vasc Med*. 2024 Dec 30;2024:8450783. doi: 10.1155/ijvm/8450783. PMID: 39764384; PMCID: PMC11703574.
23. Vahabi A, Mert M, Erdem HA, Yıldırım Şimşir I, Taşbakan Mİ, Öztürk AM. Safe Use of Hyperbaric Oxygen Therapy in the Treatment of Diabetic Foot Ulcers: A Multidisciplinary Approach to Minimize Adverse Effects. *Interdiscip Perspect Infect Dis*. 2023 Jul 25;2023:9154038. doi: 10.1155/2023/9154038. PMID: 37534331; PMCID: PMC10393520.
24. Pérez-Vielma NM, Valencia Gutiérrez MM, Sánchez Camacho JV, González Hernández JE, García ÁM, Ochoa C, Labovitz J, López MG. The effect of hyperbaric oxygen therapy on oxidative stress and

- inflammation in patients with diabetic foot ulcers: A preliminary study. *Heliyon*. 2024 Nov 20;10(23):e40586. doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e40586. PMID: 39687107; PMCID: PMC11647834.
25. Chen L, Zhang S, Da J, Wu W, Ma F, Tang C, Li G, Zhong D, Liao B. A systematic review and meta-analysis of efficacy and safety of negative pressure wound therapy in the treatment of diabetic foot ulcer. *Ann Palliat Med*. 2021 Oct;10(10):10830-10839. doi: 10.21037/apm-21-2476. PMID: 34763444.
 26. Liu Y, Liu Y, Deng J, Li W, Nie X. Fibroblast Growth Factor in Diabetic Foot Ulcer: Progress and Therapeutic Prospects. *Front Endocrinol (Lausanne)*. 2021 Oct 14;12:744868. doi: 10.3389/fendo.2021.744868. PMID: 34721299; PMCID: PMC8551859.
 27. Holl J, Kowalewski C, Zimek Z, Fiedor P, Kaminski A, Oldak T, Moniuszko M, Eljaszewicz A. Chronic Diabetic Wounds and Their Treatment with Skin Substitutes. *Cells*. 2021 Mar 15;10(3):655. doi: 10.3390/cells10030655. PMID: 33804192; PMCID: PMC8001234.
 28. Nair HK, Ahmad NW, Ismail AA, Alabed AAA, Zheming BO, Kaur G, Hassan H, Supaat NI. Maggot debridement therapy to treat hard-to-heal diabetic foot ulcers: a single-centre study. *J Wound Care*. 2021 Dec 1;30(Sup12):S30-S36. doi: 10.12968/jowc.2021.30.Sup12.S30. PMID: 34882006.
 29. Siavash M, Najjarnezhad A, Mohseni N, Abtahi SM, Karimy A, Sabzevari MH. Efficacy of Maggot Debridement Therapy on Refractory Atypical Diabetic Foot Ulcers: An Open-Label Study. *Int J Low Extrem Wounds*. 2021 Dec;20(4):315-320. doi: 10.1177/1534734620920403. Epub 2020 May 5. PMID: 32370633.
 30. Falhammar H. Diabetic foot ulcers - The time to act is now. *Indian J Med Res*. 2022 Oct-Nov;156(4&5):570-572. doi: 10.4103/ijmr.ijmr_2116_22. PMID: 36629172; PMCID: PMC10231739.
 31. Fang M, Hu J, Jeon Y, Matsushita K, Selvin E, Hicks CW. Diabetic foot disease and the risk of major clinical outcomes. *Diabetes Res Clin Pract*. 2023 Aug;202:110778. doi: 10.1016/j.diabres.2023.110778. Epub 2023 Jun 14. PMID: 37321302; PMCID: PMC10527937.